

Rare Earth Complexes with N, O-Donor Ligands. Part-I. Nitrate-Complexes of Terpositive Yttrium and Lighter Lanthanides with 2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl) Benzimidazole

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The 8-coordinate complexes of the type $[M(\text{HO-PhBzH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm}$; $n = 0.5 - 4$; $\text{HO-PhBzH} = 2\text{-(2'-hydroxyphenyl) benzimidazole}$) separate in the solid state when the metal nitrates interact with the ligand in hot ethyl acetate. Complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements and electrical conductance values. Infrared spectra reveal the presence of both coordinated (C_{2v}) and uncoordinated (D_{3h}) nitrate groups. The electronic spectra of Pr(III)-, Nd(III)-, and Sm(III)-complexes have been analysed in terms of LSJ levels.

2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl) benzimidazole (HO-Ph-BzH) is a potent bidentate N,O-donor ligand forming a six-membered chelate ring using the phenolic O and the tertiary N of the imidazole ring. Harkins *et al*¹. isolated complexes of the type $M(\text{O-PhBzH})_2$ with Co(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II), either from neutral or slightly basic ($pH \sim 8$) solution. We report here the nitrate-complexes of Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III).

Experimental

Materials : 2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl) benzimidazole was prepared as described in literature². Nitrates of La(99.99%), Ce(99.9%), Pr(99.99%), Nd(99.99%), Sm(99.99%) and Y(99.99%), obtained as hydrated crystals from the Indian Rare Earths, were used as such.

Preparation of Complexes : The metal nitrates and the ligand in 1 : 2 molar proportion, dissolved separately in hot ethyl acetate, were mixed and refluxed on steam-bath for about 15 minutes, after which the separation of the solid started. The ease of separation increased with increasing atomic number of the metal. It was further refluxed for 30-60 minutes in order to increase the particle size of the solid. The solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot ethyl acetate and dried over CaCl_2 .

Physical Measurements : A Philips resistance bridge, model PR 9500, was employed to determine the electrical conductances in solution. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made using Kahn Faraday balance, calibrated³ with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$,

Pascal's constants⁴ having been used for making diamagnetic corrections. Infrared spectra were recorded using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer in KBr discs through commercial services of the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, IIT, Madras. Electronic spectra were scanned on Cary 14 ratio-recording spectrophotometer using matched 10 mm silica cells.

Results and Discussion

The terpositive yttrium and the lighter lanthanide nitrates uniformly form the 8-coordinate dinitrato-bis-chelates of the general formula $[M(\text{HO-PhBzH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n = 0.5 - 4$), supported by the electrical conductance values of $103-137 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$ in DMF at 304°K (Table 1). The presence of lattice water in each case is ascertained by recording the loss in weight on heating upto 120° and observing no loss on further heating upto 180° .

The room-temperature magnetic moment values of Ce^{III} (2.74 BM), Pr^{III} (3.57 BM), and Nd^{III} (3.68 BM), having $^2F_{5/2}$, 3H_4 , and $^4I_{9/2}$ ground state terms, respectively, correspond to the formula⁵: $\mu_{\text{eff}} = g[J(J + 1)]^{1/2}$. However, the value of 1.75 BM observed for Sm^{III} ($^6H_{5/2}$) as against the calculated value of 0.84 BM suggests a considerable population of the excited J-levels of the metal ion⁵.

Infrared Spectra :

An uncoordinated nitrate (D_{3h}) is expected to show three IR-active fundamentals⁶, $\nu_2(A_2'')$: 831 cm^{-1} , $\nu_3(E')$: 1390 cm^{-1} , $\nu_4(E')$: 790 cm^{-1} , whereas

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TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCES (OHM⁻¹ CM² MOLE⁻¹, DMF) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (B.M.)

Complex	%M	%N	%loss in wt. 120°C*	Cond. 304°K	μ_{eff} 298°K
[LaX]NO ₃ 1.5H ₂ O	R 17.98	12.69	3.40	137	—
	F 18.15	12.52	3.60		
[CeX]NO ₃ 4H ₂ O	R 17.11	11.97	8.79	127	2.74
	F 16.93	12.00	8.40		
[PrX]NO ₃ 1.5H ₂ O	R 18.17	12.66	3.48	127	3.57
	F 18.16	12.06	3.47		
[NdX]NO ₃ 2.5H ₂ O	K 18.12	12.32	5.80	132	3.68
	P 18.08	12.01	5.54		
[SmX]NO ₃ 0.5H ₂ O**	R 19.63	12.80	1.10	118	1.75
	F 19.35	12.90	1.50		
[YX] NO ₃ 2.5H ₂ O	R 12.00	13.29	***	103	—
	F 12.46	12.82			

X=(HO—PhBzH)₂(NO₃)₂⁻; HO—PhBzH=C₁₃H₁₀N₂O; *No further loss upto 180°C
 ***Could not be done on account of low yield.

**	% C	% H
Found :	41.12	2.87
Reqd. :	40.77	2.76

a coordinated nitrate (C_{2v}) exhibits six such fundamentals⁶, $\nu_4(B_1)$: 1530-1480 cm⁻¹, $\nu_1(A_1)$: 1290 cm⁻¹, $\nu_2(A_1)$: 1030 cm⁻¹, $\nu_5(B_2)$: 810 cm⁻¹, $\nu_3(A_1)$: 740 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_6(B_1)$: 713 cm⁻¹.

The $\nu_4(B_1)$ mode in each complex appears as a doublet or a multiplet in the region 1420-1485 cm⁻¹, and the $\nu_1(A_1)$ mode falls in the range 1255-1315 cm⁻¹. The magnitude of $\nu_4-\nu_1$ ranges from 160 to 215 cm⁻¹ in these complexes, which might be considered to be in favour of the bidentate character of the C_{2v}-nitrate⁷, though this has not been considered as a good criterion to distinguish between a bidentate and a monodentate nitrate by Topping⁸ and Kawano *et al.*⁹ However, the X-ray investigations reveal that the nitrate group behaves as a bidentate ligand in the nitrate-complexes of Ce(III)¹⁰, UO₂(II)¹¹, and Th(IV)¹² and it was proposed by Cousins and Hart¹³ that, in general, nitrate exhibits a bidentate character when coordinated to the lanthanide ions. Thus we assume that in the present complexes too the nitrate groups are bidentate.

The weak bands near 1010-1035 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the $\nu_2(A_1)$ mode, those in the region 790-815 cm⁻¹ to the $\nu_5(B_2)$ mode and similar ones at 690-730 cm⁻¹ to the $\nu_6(B_1)$ mode of C_{2v}-nitrate.

The $\nu_3(E')$ bands in the range 1345-1383 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_2(A')$ ones in the region 835-860 cm⁻¹ ascertain the presence of D_{3h}-nitrate.

Harkins *et al.*¹ assigned the broad absorption band centered at 2530 cm⁻¹ to the strongly H-bonded phenolic OH. However, we propose that the strong doublet at 3210, 3280 cm⁻¹ may be ascribed to phenolic OH. There is only a broad shoulder at 2530 cm⁻¹, whereas the 3200-3300 cm⁻¹ bands are prominent ones, which are broadened and intensified in complexes containing water of crystallisation. As H-bonding lowers the stretching frequency of free phenolic OH, a lowering in $\nu(NH)$ may also

be expected and thus we propose to assign the medium intensity band of the ligand at 3030 cm⁻¹ to $\nu(NH)$ instead of the one at 3155 cm⁻¹ as proposed by Harkins *et al.*¹ On account of the presence of water of crystallisation in each complex, the 3030 cm⁻¹ band is converted, with a slight shift, into a shoulder on OH stretching bands at 3100-3500 cm⁻¹. The $\delta(HOH)$ manifests mainly as a set of shoulders in the range 1615-1665 cm⁻¹.

Electronic Spectra :

The spectrum of the sulphur-yellow Ce(terpyridyl)³⁺, recorded by Sinha¹⁴, showed a strong absorption near 401 nm, which was attributed to 4f→5d transition. A strong and continuous absorption from 450 nm towards ultraviolet by the sulphur-yellow Ce(III)-complex of HO-PhBzH in DMF also suggests a similar transition.

The spectral results for Pr(III)-, Nd(III)-, and Sm(III)-complexes in DMF have been analysed. The extent of red-shift observed in ³P₂, ³P₁, ³P₀ and ¹D₂ bands of Pr(III) in the complex in the comparison to those of the free-ion¹⁵ or the aquo-ion^{16,17} suggests a very negligible nephelauxetic effect produced by HO-PhBzH. Beyond 700 nm, the levels ¹G₄, ³F₄, ³F₃, and ³F₂ have been located, which have not been reported previously in the aquo-ion^{16,17} or the terpyridyl-complex¹⁴. Numerous bands in the region 5620-6390 cm⁻¹ remain unassigned at present.

Only a little red-shift observed in the spectral bands of Nd(III) in this complex with respect to the calculated values^{18,19} or those of the aquo-ion^{16,17,20} suggests a negligible nephelauxetic effect produced by this ligand. An idea of the extent of the nephelauxetic effect may be obtained²¹ from the shift in the transition ⁴I_{9/2}→²P_{1/2}, which, however, is obscured in the present system by charge-transfer band in the same region.

A comparison of the calculated values of J-levels of Sm^{3+} in LaCl_3 -host^{2,3} with those observed in the complex under study leads to the assignment of the levels ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$, and ${}^6\text{F}_{11/2}$. Numerous bands appear in the region 15820-23870 cm^{-1} , which have not been assigned at present. The ${}^6\text{P}$ level, which was located by Sinha^{1,4} in $\text{Sm}(\text{III})$ -terpridyl system at 24780 cm^{-1} is obscured by the charge-transfer band in the present case.

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